

Original Research

Local Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and E-government Impact on the Financial Performance

Annisa Tiara Qurrota A'yun¹
Ekaningtyas Widiastuti

Department of Management, Jenderal Soedirman University, Banyumas,
Indonesia

Received 18 February 2024 Revised 23 May 2024 Accepted 28 May 2024

Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the impact of local revenue, e-government, and capital expenditure on the financial performance of local government and how e-government mediates the effect of local revenue on financial performance. The population of this study includes 29 regencies and 6 cities in the Central Java Province, Indonesia. The purposive sampling technique was utilized to compile 76 samples. Descriptive statistical analysis and partial least squares testing with structural equation modeling were used for data analysis. The results indicate that local revenue has no significant impact on financial performance, while e-government has a positive effect, and capital expenditure has a negative effect. Moreover, local revenue has a positive impact on e-government, and e-government mediates the effect of local revenue on local government financial performance. In conclusion, this study emphasizes the importance of establishing effective budgets to improve regional revenue and invest in e-government for local governments.

Keywords: Capital expenditure, e-government, financial performance, local revenue, public finance.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: nissayunn@gmail.com

Introduction

The policy of regional autonomy grants regions both the right and responsibility to govern and manage their activities to enhance governance and community services. This policy indirectly encourages local governments to explore and maximize revenues derived from the unique potential of their regions to fund government activities. Regional independence achieved is a sign of effective government performance, which may be quantified by analyzing financial results and qualitatively by establishing societal welfare (Silitonga et al., 2021).

Data from the Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia (BPS) indicates that the regional income of regencies and cities in Central Java Province fluctuated between 2015 and 2020, suggesting that regional autonomy implementation in Central Java may not be effectively executed. This is further supported by the Central Java Province region's poor financial performance, which shows a low degree of regional independence given their heavy reliance on federal funding. Among the regencies and cities in Central Java Province, Surakarta City experienced a sharp decline in average revenue growth in 2020, falling by 23.9 percent, which highlights the significant fluctuations in regional revenue growth in Central Java.

Based on data from the Ministry of Finance Directorate General of Treasury of Indonesia (Kementerian Keuangan Direktorat Jenderal Perbendaharaan), the fiscal decentralization ratio in Central Java for 2021 reveals that 23 local governments are classified as having a low regional financial capability level score, suggesting that local revenue (PAD) realization has not been fully optimized. The low realization of local revenue indicates that the region has not maximized revenue from sources such as taxes and fees, as well as locally owned enterprises (BUMD) profit sharing. Moreover, local revenue (PAD) is crucial as it provides income from the regency's or city's original economic sources, reducing dependence on central funding and enhancing financial performance by maximizing regional own-source income (Antari & Sedana, 2018).

The issues highlighted by the data from the Central Bureau of Statistics Indonesia (BPS) and the Ministry of Finance Directorate General of Treasury of Indonesia (Kementerian Keuangan Direktorat Jenderal Perbendaharaan) indicate a pressing need for urgent action to address the challenges facing Central Java Province. These issues pose a significant challenge in achieving effective governance and enhancing financial performance. Local governments need to take proactive measures to optimize their revenue collection efforts by exploring and maximizing revenues derived from the unique potential of their regions.

Local governments also have to enhance public services to achieve effective governance. The construction of public sector facilities has a significant effect on regional revenue growth since it increases revenues by providing adequate facilities (Antari & Sedana, 2018). The use of technology in the implementation of government policy can help support government processes. Implementation of good governance through e-government can encourage active community participation, reach wider communities and regions, and reduce fraudulent transactions. As a result, e-government improves local

government performance (Ulfi et al., 2022). In addition, the implementation of accrual accounting in public sector organizations will increase government accountability and develop better decision-making in government, resulting in enhanced local government performance (Hasthoro & Sunardi, 2016). Thus, the government must improve the execution of good governance by improving the quality of government services through the use of information technology to boost government efficiency and effectiveness.

Capital expenditure pertains to the allocation of funds by a regional government towards initiatives that contribute to the growth of regional assets or wealth associated with general administrative operations, such as maintenance expenditures (Leki et al., 2018). Capital expenditure can be a solution to the problem of low regional financial performance because regional revenue can be increased through capital expenditure by investing in financial sources that follow the specificities of the region (Astuti & Mimba, 2016).

Insufficient public sector facilities and inefficient government processes hinder regional revenue growth and overall performance. In addition, the lack of robust governance mechanisms, community participation, and accountability, along with fraudulent transactions, undermines the effectiveness of local government operations. The low regional financial performance requires the identification and implementation of strategies such as capital expenditure and accrual accounting to address these shortcomings and strengthen the financial viability and performance of local governments.

Thus, this research examines; the influence of local revenue, e-government, and capital expenditure on the financial performance of Central Java's local government; the influence of local revenue on e-government implementation; and the mediating role of e-government on the influence of local revenue on the financial performance of Central Java local government.

Theoretical Framework

Agency Theory

Agency theory asserts a relationship in which one or more individuals, referred to as "principals," hire an agent to provide a service and delegate decision-making authority to them (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Halim and Abdullah (2006) suggest that agency theory is relevant to the public organizational sector, as the principal agrees, either implicitly or explicitly, with a third party, the agent, to ensure that the agent can execute the principal's instructions or conduct themselves as expected. This indicates that the principal transfers authority to the agent within the context of agency theory.

Halim and Abdullah (2006) posit that legislation serves as an agreement between the executive, legislature, and general public. It encompasses all obligations that the government participants must fulfill through laws and regulations. The regional budget lays the groundwork for financing public services. Furthermore, as the executive, the government assumes responsibility for communicating the outcomes of its efforts to the principal, which is the general public (Oktaviani & Indra Arza, 2020).

Signaling Theory

According to Spence's (1973) signaling theory, the purpose of a sender's signal is to convey useful information to the recipient. In the public sector, the government strives to provide a positive signal to the public (Evans III & Patton, 1987). Financial reports can serve as a positive signal to the community, encouraging them to support their local government. Public performance reporting, on the other hand, is a means of public accountability for government performance outcomes, fulfilling the government's pledge to inform the public (Verawaty, 2017).

Information technology has the potential to enhance the reporting of government performance. Through the implementation of e-government programs that leverage information technology, the distribution of information can be streamlined and made more accessible to the public. Furthermore, the adoption of e-government initiatives can promote transparency in government financial performance, as noted by Hasthoro and Sunardi (2016).

Local government financial performance, local revenue, and e-government

Local government financial performance and local revenue

According to Antari and Sedana (Antari & Sedana, 2018), by maximizing its regional income, a region can lessen its reliance on central support and enhance its financial performance. Therefore, regional original income greatly determines the independence of local governments. The maximum utilization of potential financial sources in the regions is expected to increase local revenue, which in turn will improve regional performance.

Antari and Sedana (2018), Leki et al. (2018), Sari and Wati (2022), and other researchers have found that local revenue has a positive impact on regional financial performance. This discussion leads to the conclusion that local revenue is a highly precise predictor of the financial performance of local governments.

H₁; Local revenue has a positive effect on the local government's financial performance.

Local government financial performance and e-government

E-government denotes an approach where governments leverage cutting-edge information and communication technologies, with a particular emphasis on internet-based applications, to facilitate more accessible information and government service access for citizens and businesses. This approach aims to improve service quality and broaden opportunities for engagement in democratic institutions and processes (Sharma, 2017). Through the automation and computerization of government administration, e-government improves government performance by increasing government accountability. The government can strategize internally using e-government across departments, processes, and functional government (Ndou, 2004).

It is anticipated that the region's e-government development will enable more transparent, effective, and efficient government processes, enhancing Indonesia's regional financial performance. Ulfi et al. (2022) claim that the region's financial performance is greatly impacted by the region's adoption of e-government. According to Sutopo et al. (2017), using e-government can increase Indonesia's government administration's effectiveness. Based on this reasoning, it may be concluded that e-government significantly improves local governments' financial performance.

H₂: E-government has a positive effect on local government financial performance.

E-government and local revenue

Economic prosperity, education, urbanization, people's freedom, government efficacy, and relationships among economic users all have an impact on e-government (Kim, 2007). The substantial expenses that the government must incur to adopt e-government in local government must be supported by the availability of adequate funding. As a result, the bigger the regional own-source revenue, the more funds are available to support the government's construction of infrastructure and facilities that support e-government. According to the findings of Sipahutar and Sutaryo (2017), Ikhsan et al. (2021), and Novitasari et al. (2022), local revenue has a positive impact on e-government. This study proposes the following hypothesis based on previous research and theory:

H₃: Local revenue has a positive effect on e-government.

Local government financial performance, local revenue, and e-government

Based on the previous discussion, it can be concluded that e-government improves local government performance. This is because e-government helps the government improve its efficiency and accountability. According to Ulfi et al. (2022), the higher a local government's e-government score, the better its financial performance. The development of e-government is a crucial undertaking that requires substantial funding from the government. Adequate funding would enable the government to create a modern, efficient, and reliable e-government infrastructure that would cater to the needs of the citizens. As a consequence, the government must have sufficient funds to finance e-government-based government activities. Local revenue has a positive impact on e-government, according to research by Sipahutar and Sutaryo (2017), Ikhsan et al. (2021), and Novitasari et al. (2022). The following hypothesis is put forth in this study based on the description of the theory and prior studies:

H₄: E-government mediates the effect of local revenue on local government financial performance.

Local government financial performance and capital expenditure

Rapid infrastructure development in the regions, induced by an elevated proportion of capital expenditure, can promote investment activities in the regions, which can affect regional revenue growth in the future, boost the regional economy, and provide jobs for the local population. Enhancing the local economy means raising local revenue, which has beneficial impacts on financial performance.

Capital spending has a positive impact on regional financial performance, according to studies by Andirfa et al. (2016), Astiti and Mimba (2016), Mulyani and Wibowo (2017), Leki et al. (2018), and Setiawan and Winarna (2022). The following hypothesis is put forth by this study based on prior theories and studies:

H₅: Capital expenditure has a positive effect on regional financial performance

The conceptual model of this research is shown in the the Fig. 1 below.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Methodology

Sample Selection and Data Selection

This study employs annual secondary data for the 2020–2022 time frame, including APBD realization reports and SPBE evaluation results for the regional governments of the regencies and cities of Central Java Province. Thus, this study is quantitative research and uses a causality technique (comparative causal). The PLS test was chosen because it does not rely on overly broad assumptions, and the results of the analytical procedure are thought to be robust. PLS-SEM may evaluate routes with all variables in a regression model while performing an analysis using PLS.

The research population in this study consists of all the regencies and city governments of Central Java Province. With the criteria of the regencies and city governments of Central Java Province reporting the implementation of the APBD budget and SPBE Evaluation Results for the period of 2020–2022, a purposive sampling methodology was used to determine the sample for this study. The SMART PLS 4.0 analytic tool is used in this study's partial least squares data analysis method. The equations of this research are as follows:

$$Y = \alpha_1 + c_1 \text{Local revenue} + c_2 \text{E - government} + c_3 \text{Capital expenditure} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{E - government} = \alpha_2 + a \text{PAD} \quad (2)$$

where:

- α Coefficient of variable X to M
- α_1 Equation I constant
- α_2 Equation II constant
- c Coefficient of variable X to Y (equation I)
- Y Local Government Financial Performance Level

Variable Measurement

This study's independent variables include capital expenditures (X3), e-government (X2), and local revenue (X1), which were gathered from APBD realization data from BPK RI and DJPK RI as well as the SPBE Evaluation Report from MENPAN-RB RI. The study's financial performance is measured using efficiency ratios based on APBD realization data. The e-government variable in this study is a mediating variable and is measured by the SPBE Index. The measurement formulas for each variable are as follows:

- Financial performance: $\frac{\text{total realized regional expenditure}}{\text{total realized regional revenue}} \times 100\%$
- Local revenue: realization of local revenue
- Capital expenditure: realization of capital expenditure
- E-government: SPBE Index

Findings

Descriptive Statistic

Based on the results of the data processed, the results of descriptive statistical analysis are as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistic of Data

	N	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Deviation
EGOV	76	2.86	2.13	3.73	0.346
KK	105	0.96	0.828	1.164	0.053
LR	105	462,252,587,520	219,539,400,332	3,152,380,000,000	382,248,800,331
Ln_LR	105	26.732	26.114	28.779	0.416
CE	105	290,251,964,087	75,180,000,000	1,064,380,000,000	149,530,305,800
Ln_CE	105	26.288	25.043	27.693	0.454

The results of the descriptive statistics calculations in Table 1 explain the number of samples (N) of 105 for the variables local revenue (X1), capital expenditures (X2), and local government financial performance (Y). Meanwhile, the number of samples (N) for the e-government variable (M) was 76. The difference in sample size between the e-government variable of 76 samples and the local revenue variable, capital expenditure, and regional financial performance variable of 105 samples occurs due to a missing value or loss of e-government variable data, which is proxied by the SPBE index totaling 29 data points. This happened due to incomplete data in the SPBE Evaluation Report for the

regencies and cities of Central Java Province for 2020 and 2022. Therefore, 29 observations were deleted, so a total of 76 samples were obtained.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics explain that the number of samples (N) of the local revenue variable (X1) is 105. The average local revenue value is 462,252,587,520, with the lowest value being 219,539,400,332, the largest value being 3,152,380,000,000, and a standard deviation of 382,248,800,331. Meanwhile, the results of the transformation of the natural logarithm data for the local revenue variable (X1) have an average of 26.732, the lowest value is 26.114, the highest value is 28.779, and the standard deviation is 0.416.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of 74 Samples Data

	N	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Deviation
EGOV	74	2.8664	2.13	3.73	0.3449
FP	74	0.9527	0.8410	1.0469	0.0427
LR	74	484,412,258,515	238,638,994,331	3,152,380,000,000	408,696,472,147
Ln_LR	74	26.7759	26.1982	28.7792	0.4217
CE	74	305,590,654,753	75,180,000,000	1,064,380,000,000	160,663,063,943
Ln_CE	74	26.3387	25.0432	27.6934	0.4561

Partial Least Square

Structural Model Test (Inner Model Test)

To ascertain the correlation between the constructs, significant value, and R-square of the research model, inner model testing was carried out. R2 for endogenous constructs and path coefficient values for external constructs are used in PLS to evaluate the structural model. The relevance of the model is then evaluated using the t-statistic value. Figure 2 displays the study's structural model.

Figure 2. Structural Model Output

R-square Test

Table 3. R-Square Test Result

	R-square	R-square adjusted
E-Government	0.037	0.024
FP	0.17	0.134

According to the R-square table, the local government financial performance variable (Y) reflects a value of 0.17. This indicates that 17% of the variation in the local government's financial performance can be explained by the local revenue (X1), capital expenditure (X2), and e-government (M) variables, with the remaining 83% not being covered by this study. Considering an R2 value of 0.037, the e-government variable can be explained by the local revenue variable to the level of 3.7%; the remaining 96.3% cannot be explained by this study.

Q-Square Test

Table 4. Q-Square Test Result

	Q ² predict	RMSE	MAE
EGOV	0.02	1.022	0.833

The PLS model's assessment is evaluated by its predictive relevance or Q-square value. The model has predictive relevance if the Q-square value is greater than zero.

Hypothesis Test

Table 5. Path Coefficient Test

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
EGOV -> FP	-0.303	-0.294	0.117	2.598	0.009
LN_CE -> FP	0.343	0.335	0.157	2.188	0.029
LN_LR -> EGOV	0.193	0.189	0.091	2.121	0.034
LN_LR -> FP	-0.259	-0.259	0.148	1.746	0.081

There is no significant correlation between local revenue and regional financial performance, according to the t-statistic score of 1.746 < 1.96. The initial sample estimate value of -0.259 suggests that the association between local revenue and the financial performance of local governments could be interpreted negatively. However, the local government financial performance variable uses regional financial efficiency ratios, which illustrate the comparison between the large costs incurred by the government to obtain revenue and the actual income received, so that a small or low ratio value explains efficient regional financial performance. Conversely, the greater the efficiency ratio of regional financial performance, the more inefficient regional financial performance is. Therefore, the negative path coefficient of local revenue on local government financial performance explains the positive. Based on the result, hypothesis 1 is rejected.

The t-statistic score of $2.598 > 1.96$ indicates a significant relationship between e-government and local government financial performance. E-government's positive correlation with local government financial performance was explained by the initial sample estimate value of -0.303 . Hypothesis 2 is accepted based on the results of PLS data processing.

The t-statistic value of $2.121 > 1.96$ and the initial sample estimate value of 0.193 shows that the association between local revenue and e-government is significant and that it trends in a positive direction. The results support the acceptance of Hypothesis 3.

The findings of the study examining the impact of local income and e-government on the financial performance of local governments are important, suggesting that e-government factors play a mediating role in the relationship between local revenue and financial performance. The outcomes of the PLS data processing provide support for hypothesis 4.

The impact of capital expenditures on local government financial performance is significant, as indicated by the path analysis results, with an original sample estimate value of 0.029 and a t-statistic value of $2.188 > 1.96$. These findings suggest that there is a negative correlation between capital expenditure and the financial performance of local governments. The PLS data processing results show that hypothesis 5 is not supported.

Conclusion and Discussion

This study indicates that local revenue has no significant effect on regional financial performance. According to agency theory, the government (agent) will work to raise regional income to fulfill its duty to society (principal) by producing good government performance. Regional original income, however, had no discernible impact on regional financial performance in this study. This demonstrates that regional financial performance has not improved despite local revenue collected by the regions. This may occur because of the Regency/City of Central Java Province's local government's sustained low local revenue, which has prevented it from improving the financial performance of the region. Another thing that could be a factor that does not affect local revenue or regional financial performance is the allocation of regional income, which is not ideal in terms of local government investment, so it does not increase regional revenue.

E-government in this study has a positive effect on local government financial performance, and better e-government implementation can improve local government financial performance. E-government facilitates community needs such as the ease of electronic payment services and increasing regional investment opportunities (Kareem & Haseeni, 2015). In addition, e-government also enables the public to discuss and provide feedback on public policies to government officials and other citizens, thus supporting a transparent, responsive, and efficient government (Manoharan & Ingrams, 2018). Therefore, the higher the transparency of government performance, the more it encourages the government to decide on financial policies that can improve regional financial performance.

The results of this study reveal that the higher the local revenue, the more motivated the government is to disclose the results of its financial performance to the public through information publication. The community, as a principal in agency theory, has the right to claim the right to obtain public information regarding the performance of the government as an agent appointed by the community to administer the government. In addition, the high local revenue indicates that the government has succeeded in achieving self-reliant governance, thereby encouraging the government to disclose financial information.

This study demonstrates how the impact of local revenue on the financial performance of local governments is mediated by e-government. The study supports the agency theory, which determines that the government tries to fulfill the needs of society, while also supporting the signaling theory, which predicts that the government tries to send a positive signal to the community over government performance, as evidenced by the positive effects of local revenue on e-government and e-government's positive effects on local government financial performance.

The findings of this study clarify the negative effect of capital expenditure on local government financial performance, i.e., the higher the regional government's allocation of capital expenditure, the lower its financial performance will be. The detrimental impact of capital expenditures on regional financial performance implies that the more capital expenditures a regional authority issues, the more inefficient its operations become. This could occur when government capital expenditures do not immediately generate profits.

Recommendations

Due to the lack of audited APBD realization data for the 2022 fiscal year, this study uses both audited and unaudited data. APBD realization data that has been audited is preferable for future research because it has been verified by the Indonesian Financial Audit Agency and therefore is more accurate. Additionally, a lot of data for the e-government variable cannot be found, resulting in a lot of missing values in the data processing for this research.

Future studies should aim to assess the impact of e-government on regional financial performance using more comprehensive data. Additionally, this study's e-government variable's coefficient of determination was just 3.7%, whereas the regional financial performance variable's was 17%. This suggests that e-government and regional financial success are still influenced by additional factors or variables. It is recommended for future research if other factors were included, such as internal auditor competency, GDRP, general allocation funds, and special allocation funds.

References

- Andirfa, M., Basri, H., & Majid, M. S. A. (2016). Pengaruh Belanja Modal, Dana Perimbangan dan Pendapatan Asli Daerah Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Kabupaten dan Kota di Provinsi Aceh. *Jurnal Magister Akuntansi*, 30–38.
- Antari, N. P. G. S., & Sedana, I. B. P. (2018). Pengaruh Pendapatan Asli Daerah Dan Belanja Modal Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Pemerintah Daerah. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 7(2), 1080. <https://doi.org/10.24843/ejmunud.2018.v7.i02.p19>

- Astiti, D. N. Y., & Mimba, N. P. S. H. (2016). Pengaruh Belanja Rutin Dan Belanja Modal Pada Kinerja Keuangan Pemerintah Daerah. *E-Jurnal Akuntansi Universitas Udayana*, 14(3), 1924–1950.
- Evans III, H. J., & Patton, M. J. (1987). Discussion of Signaling and Monitoring in Public-Sector Accounting. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 25(1987), 159. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2491084>
- Halim, A., & Abdullah, S. (2006). Hubungan dan Masalah Keagenan di Pemerintah Daerah: Sebuah Peluang Penelitian Anggaran dan AKuntansi. *Jurnal Akuntansi Pemerintahan*, 2(1), 53–64.
- Hasthoro, H. A., & Sunardi, S. (2016). Tata Kelola Publik Dan Kinerja Keuangan Pemerintah Daerah Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis*, 18(1), 53. <https://doi.org/10.24914/jeb.v19i1.480>
- Ikhshan, S., Afiah, N. N., & Yudianto, I. (2021). Analysis of Factors Affecting the Level Of E-Government Implementation in West Java. *JASa (Jurnal Akuntansi, Audit Dan Sistem Informasi Akuntansi)*, 5(1), 123–134. <https://doi.org/10.36555/jasa.v5i1.1491>
- Jensen, M., & Meckling, W. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3, 283–303. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511817410.023>
- Kareem, M. A., & Haseeni, Z. J. (2015). E-Government and Its Impact on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations ISSN 2348-7585 (Online)*, 3(1), 664–672.
- Kim, C. K. (2007). A cross-national analysis of global e-government. *Public Organization Review*, 7(4), 317–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11115-007-0040-5>
- Leki, Y., Naukoko, A. T., & Sumua, J. (2018). Pengaruh Pendapatan Asli Daerah Dan Belanja Modal Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Pada Pemerintah Kabupaten Halmahera Barat. *Jurnal Berkala Ilmiah Efisiensi*, 18(5), 164–174.
- Manoharan, A. P., & Ingrams, A. (2018). Conceptualizing E-Government from Local Government Perspectives. *State and Local Government Review*, 50(1), 56–66. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0160323x18763964>
- Mulyani, S., & Wibowo, H. (2017). Pengaruh Belanja Modal, Ukuran Pemerintah Daerah, Intergovernmental Revenue Dan Pendapatan Asli Daerah Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan (Kabupaten/ Kota Di Provinsi Jawa Tengah, Tahun 2012-2015). *Kompartemen*, XV(1), 57–66.
- Ndou, V. D. (2004). E - Government for Developing Countries: Opportunities and Challenges. *The Electronic Journal of Information Systems in Developing Countries*, 18(1), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1681-4835.2004.tb00117.x>
- Novitasari, E., Dewi, F. G., & Oktavia, R. (2022). Determinants of E-Government Implementation in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 22(19), 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2022/v22i1930656>

- Oktaviani, S., & Indra Arza, F. (2020). Pengaruh Kompetisi Politik, Pendapatan Asli Daerah, Dana Alokasi Umum, Dan Opini Audit Terhadap Implementasi E-Government. *Jurnal Eksplorasi Akuntansi*, 2(3), 3312–3326. <https://doi.org/10.24036/jea.v2i3.284>
- Pranestianegara, W., & Sari, R. P. (2022). Fenomenologi Revaluasi Aset di Sektor Publik. *Owner*, 6(3), 3139–3150. <https://doi.org/10.33395/owner.v6i3.1011>
- Setiawan, D., & Winarna, J. (2022). The Determinants of Local Government Performance. *Quality - Access to Success*, 23(186), 93–97. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/23.186.12>
- Sharma, S. (2017). E-Government in Digital Era: Concept, Practice, and Development. *International Journal of Science, Technology and Management*, 6(22), 771–777.
- Silitonga, N., Manurung, H. A., Mayangsari, S., & Sormin, P. (2021). The Moderating Effect Of Regional Independence On The Effect Of Financing Policies, Capital Expenditure And Transfer Fund Towards The Performance Of Local Governments. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(3), 5239–5251. <https://doi.org/10.17762/turcomat.v12i3.2153>
- Sipahutar, R. I. S., & Sutaryo. (2017). Faktor-Faktor Penentu Implementasi E-Government Pemerintah Daerah Di Indonesia. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Dan Keuangan*, 5(2), 1393–1408.
- Spence, M. (1973). Job Market Signaling. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 87(3), 355–374.
- Sutopo, B., Wulandari, T. R., Adiati, A. K., & Saputra, D. A. (2017). E-government, audit opinion, and performance of local government administration in Indonesia. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 11(4), 6–22. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v11i4.2>
- Ulfi, I. H., Afiah, N. N., & Mulyani, S. (2022). Implikasi Belanja Modal dan E-Government Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Pemerintah Daerah di Bangka Belitung dan Sumatera Selatan. 5(2), 70–83.
- Veraway. (2017). Determinan Transparansi Informasi Keuangan Daerah Melalui E-Government Pemerintah Daerah Di Sumatera Selatan. *Akuisisi: Jurnal Akuntansi*, 13(2), 92–107. <https://doi.org/10.24127/akuisisi.v13i2.172>

<p>COPYRIGHTS ©2024 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.</p>	
<p>HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE A'yun, A. T., Najmudin, N., & Widiastuti, E. (2024). Local Revenue, Capital Expenditure, and E-government Impact on the Financial Performance. <i>International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics</i>, 11(8), 1045-1057. DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13323485 URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_201742.html</p>	